

IONIZATION AND CONFORMATIONAL EQUILIBRIA OF CITRIC ACID FROM *AB INITIO* CALCULATIONS AND NMR TITRATION

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Abstract

Despite its biological, environmental and industrial relevance of citric acid, its microscopic ionization equilibria is still controversial due to the complex interplay between conformational and ionization degrees of freedom. We study citric acid roto-micro-speciation by means of *ab initio* MP2 calculations using the SMD polarizable continuum model for the solvent. Conformational structures and probabilities of the microscopic ionization states were obtained for citric acid in solution. In addition, NMR titration data of citric acid have been used to determine micro-states probabilities, together with microscopic binding parameters. In contrast with previous methods, we obtain the micro-speciation without consideration of other molecules rather than citric acid. Both approaches allow discussing ionization mechanism in full detail. It is concluded that the first ionization step takes place with greatest probably at the central carboxyl group, in agreement with previous works based on selective

blocking of the carboxylic groups by forming the corresponding methyl esters. For the di-ionized form, *ab initio* results indicate that the most probable state is that corresponding to two consecutive charged carboxylic groups. This result is counter-intuitive if the molecule is analyzed ignoring the conformational structure. The same conclusion is obtained from NMR titration. In this case the symmetric di-ionized form is almost non-existent. Regarding the conformational details, it is shown that the most extended conformation is the most stable at low and high pH corresponding to the non-ionized and fully ionized form, whereas at intermediate pH the molecule adopts also more compact conformations.

1 Introduction

Citric acid is an important molecule involved in a wide range of biological, industrial and environmental processes[1]. Citrate is also relevant in colloidal sciences, where it is used as a common stabilizer and a reducing agent in the synthesis of gold nanoparticles[2]. It is also involved in differential adsorption on crystal surfaces leading to differential growing of crystal geometries[3]. *[Posar més aplicacions?]* All these properties are pH-dependent, so that a detailed knowledge of the ionization mechanism of this small molecule is necessary. Most of studies of the ionization properties of citric acid have been approached within the macroscopic picture. Each protonation step is described by an equilibrium reaction characterized by a macroscopic equilibrium constant. Citric acid has three ionizable carboxylic groups, and the corresponding macroscopic dissociation constants have been mostly measured using potentiometry, in a wide range of ionic strengths and temperatures, in presence of different ground electrolytes [4, 5, 6, 7]. However, in the macroscopic approach no information is provided about the population of the micro-states, in which the protonation state of every individual site is specified [8, 9, 10]. In the case of citric acid, there is still controversy about the micro-state populations compatible with the macroscopic equilibrium constants [11, 12, 13].

Two approaches have been applied in the determination of the micro-speciation of small molecules. In the so-called 'deductive' methods, the molecule is modified so that one or several ionizable groups are blocked. The non-blocked groups are supposed to have the same ionization properties as the original molecule. This is the weakest part of the approach, since changes in the chemical structure of the molecule could modify the conformational and thus the chemical environment of the rest of the groups [10, 14]. In the case of citric acid, several authors have selectively blocked the carboxylic groups forming the corresponding methyl esters [11, 12, 13]. The reported results, although consistent with the value of the macroscopic constants, differ in the micro-state populations. Loewenstein *et al.* [11] obtained that the asymmetrical mono-ionized molecule is predominant. However, Martin [13] obtains that the most abundant is the symmetrical form. Concerning the di-ionized molecule, in Martin's work the symmetrical form is the most abundant, while in Pearce *et al.* work [12] the asymmetric form prevails.

A second approach is the use of spectroscopic techniques sensitive to the

protonation of individual sites [*Al review de Borkovec hi ha cites?*] which do not perturb the conformational structure of the molecule. Among them, high resolution NMR is probably the most versatile and has been widely used in the micro-speciation of a wide range of ionizable molecules ranging from proteins to small molecules[8, 9, 10, 15, 16, 17, 18]. The chemical shift of a nucleus located in the proximity of a ionizable group is sensitive to its protonation state. Actually, it has been shown that, if the conformational equilibria are fast enough, the chemical shift is a linear combination of the degree of protonation of the neighbouring sites [8, 19], so that measures of the chemical shift *vs* pH provides information about the micro-speciation of the molecule. Citric acid is a AB spin system with two sets of coupled methylene protons, depicted in Fig. 1b. Moore and Sillereud measured the pH dependence of the high resolution NMR spectra, including both the chemical shift and the spin-spin coupling [20]. The authors were able to successfully determine the value of the macroscopic constants. However, no attempt of micro-speciation was made, which is performed in the present work.

On the other hand, one of the challenges that citric acid presents is the strong coupling of conformational and ionization degrees of freedom. Thus, a detailed knowledge of the protonation mechanism of citric acid should include the characterization of the conformational equilibria which justify the micro-speciation, including the possible formation of intramolecular hydrogen bonds ~~and the possibility of sharing of protons between ionizable groups~~. Conformational properties of citric acid has been previously analyzed by Khan et al. [21]. They first generate conformations of citric acid and its dissociated forms using a Monte Carlo method with a classical force field. The low energy conformers were optimized with B3LYP/6-31+G level in gas phase. The polarized continuum model was used to perform single point solvent calculations. Wrigth et al. performed Carr-Parrinello molecular dynamics simulations [22] for the completely deprotonated form of citric acid to obtain force-field parameters. They applied the obtained parameters to study the conformational stability by long classical molecular dynamics simulations. In our study we perform *ab initio* MP2 optimizations in water using the SMD polarizable continuum model for solvent [23] to fully characterize the conformational properties of this molecule at the four possible forms, corresponding to charge states 0, -1, -2 and -3.

The present work combines the information obtained from *ab initio* calculations and NMR data to explain the micro-speciation of citric acid. In addition, NMR data of citric acid [20] has been analyzed with the cluster expansion method [16] to obtain all microscopic ionization constants as well as the probabilities of the different microstates. The information obtained from both approaches allows discussing ionization mechanism of this molecule in full detail. In contrast with previous studies of the ionization mechanism of citric acid that use related ester molecules [11, 12, 13], we present a detailed study of the microspeciation without need of information from related molecules whose conformational properties could be non completely equivalent to the corresponding to citric acid.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Macrostates, Microstates and Roto-microstates

A particular conformational and ionization state, or *roto-microstate*, of a molecule with n protonated sites is fully characterized by the probability $p_n(c, s, a_H)$, where a_H denotes the proton activity, s the protonation state and c a particular conformational state. The ionization state q is defined by a set of variables $q = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_N\}$, being N the number of ionizable sites, which can take the values $q_i = 1$ if the site is ionized (deprotonated) and $q_i = 0$ if it is protonated. The choice of the protonation variables is not unique. For instance, as in previous works, one could have chosen the variables $s_i = 1 - q_i$, i.e., $s_i = 1$ if the site i is protonated and 0 otherwise. However, we consider that, since citric acid is a polyacid, binding parameters such as interaction energies are easier to interpret in terms of interaction of charged ionized groups rather than between protons. $n = \sum_{i=1, \dots, N} s_i$ is the total number of protonated groups and define a *macrostate* n . It can be shown that $p(c, s, a_H)$ can be expressed in the following form

$$p(c, s, a_H) = \pi_n(c, s) P_n(a_H) \quad (1)$$

$\pi_n(c, q)$ represents the conditional probability of a roto-microstate provided that belongs to a *macrostate* n . $P_n(a_H)$ is the macrostate probability and it is given by

$$P_n(a_H) = \frac{\overline{K}_n a_H^n}{\Xi} \quad (2)$$

where $\overline{K}_n$ are the macroscopic protonation constants and $\Xi = \sum_{i=0, \dots, N} \overline{K}_i a_H^i$ (with $\overline{K}_0 = 1$) is the semi-grandcanonic partition function. $\overline{K}_n$ corresponds to the process of binding n protons to the fully deprotonated molecule, and characterize the macroscopic description, which does not differentiate which individual ionizable site is ionized. Note that Eq. (1) expresses that the dependence on the pH of the roto-microstate probabilities comes only through the macrostates probabilities, while the conditional probabilities are pH independent[9, 24]. For carboxylic acids as citric acid, the experimental quantities currently reported are the dissociation pK_i -values, which corresponds to the process of releasing the i th proton, i.e., the deprotonation of the species which $N - i + 1$ protons. K_i and $\overline{K}_n$ are related by $pK_i = -\log K_i = \log(\overline{K}_{N-i+1}/\overline{K}_{N-i})$. Finally, a *microstate* s is defined as the set of roto-microstates with the same ionization state.[24] The microstate probability is given by

$$\tilde{\pi}_n(q) = \sum_c \pi_n(c, q) \quad (3)$$

and represents the conditional probability of a microstate s within a macrostate n . The microstate probabilities are related to the microstate free energy

$$\tilde{\pi}_n(q) = \frac{e^{-\beta F(q)}}{\sum_s e^{-\beta F(q)}} \quad (4)$$

which can be expressed as a so-called cluster expansion

$$\frac{\beta F(q)}{\ln 10} = \sum_i pk_i q_i + \frac{1}{2!} \sum_{i,j} \epsilon_{ij} q_i q_j + \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{i,j,k} \lambda_{ijk} q_i q_j q_k + \dots \quad (5)$$

where $\beta = 1/k_B T$, pk_i is the microscopic dissociation constant of the site i ; ϵ_{ij} is the pair interaction parameter between the charged sites i and j ; λ_{ijk} represents the triplet interaction parameters, etc. The pk_i , ϵ_{ij} , λ_{ijk} cluster parameters do not depend on the conformational state, and they are proper averages of the roto-microstates [24, 25]. In the case of citric acid, the cluster expansion can be simplified using the symmetry of the molecule. Since the two terminal carboxylic groups are equivalent, the cluster expansion remains

$$\frac{\beta F(q)}{\ln 10} = pk_1 (q_1 + q_3) + pk_2 q_2 + \epsilon_{12} (q_1 q_2 + q_2 q_3) + \epsilon_{13} q_1 q_3 + \lambda q_1 q_2 q_3 \quad (6)$$

In this work, both roto-microstate and microstate probabilities are evaluated by *ab initio* calculations. The fully protonated form of the citric acid was first prepared in the extended conformation (Fig. 1a). The methylene carbons of the chain are denoted as C₁, C₂ and C₃. All three carbons are bonded to a carboxylic group. In addition, C₂ is also bonded to a hydroxyl group. These three carbons form a skeleton of the molecule in which, two ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 dihedral angles could be defined for the rotational state of the C₁–C₂ and C₂–C₃ bonds, respectively. The rotation of sp³–sp³ bonds results in three possible minima. Here, they are indicated as *trans* or *t* ($\phi_i \simeq 0$); *gauche*⁺ or, for abbreviation, *g*⁺ ($\phi_i \simeq 60$); and *gauche*[–] or *g*[–] ($\phi_i \simeq -60$). **check** We have chosen Flory criteria to assign the sign of the rotations, for which the state⁺ is chosen as rotating the bond in the counterclock direction[26]. Besides the rotational states of the central bonds, one has to take into account the possible dispositions of the carboxylic groups, which determine, for instance, the formation of intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Thus, for *tt*, *tg* and *gg* conformations of the ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 dihedral angles, different orientations of the carboxylic groups were explored in order to check the viability of intramolecular hydrogen bonds among the hydroxyl and the three carboxylic groups. With these criteria at hand, conformations were generated in a systematic way. The geometry of the conformers were optimized at MP2 level with 6-311++G(d,p) basis set using the SMD water model. Several studies [27, 28, 29] show the accuracy and performance of the SMD implicit model for calculations of solvation free energies. Frequency calculations in solution were performed on all structures to confirm the absence of imaginary vibrational modes. The calculation of the vibrational contribution to the free energy in solution is required for cases where liquid and gas-phase structures differ appreciably or when stationary points present in solution do not exist in gas phase [30]. Free energies and roto-microstate probabilities were obtained by performing thermochemistry calculations computed at 298K. Microstate probabilities were calculated using eqns. 3 and 4. The same approach has been used for the rest of macrostates: the mono-ionized, di-ionized and

fully ionized forms. For every microstate, the geometry of the possible conformational states is optimized and free energies and roto-microstate probabilities calculated. All *ab initio* calculations were carried out with Gaussian 09[31].

2.2 NMR titrations

If the conformational and protonation equilibria are fast enough, it can be rigorously shown that the chemical shift of a particular atom α close to a ionizable group is given by the average of the chemical shifts of the possible roto-microstates of the molecule[32]. The simple form of the NMR spectrum of citric acid, shown in fig.1 reveals that this hypothesis is fulfilled by citric acid [20]. The chemical of an nucleus close to an ionizable group at a given pH, $\delta_\alpha(a_H)$ is then given by[10]

$$\delta_\alpha(a_H) = \sum_{c,s} \delta'_\alpha(c,s) p_n(c,s,a_H) \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) together with (1) leads to

$$\delta_\alpha(a_H) = \sum_{n=0,\dots,N} \tilde{\delta}_{\alpha n} P_n(a_H) \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\delta}_{\alpha n} = \sum_{c,s} \delta'_\alpha(c,s) \pi_n(c,s) \delta_{n,\sum_{i=1,\dots,N} s_i}$ is the average of the chemical shifts corresponding to the same macrostate and $\delta_{n,\sum_{i=1,\dots,N} s_i}$ is the Kronecker delta, which takes the value 1 when there are exactly n protons, and 0 otherwise. Equation (8), together with (2), allows determining the macroscopic constants by fitting the experimental chemical shifts as a function of the pH. This information can be also available by potentiometric titration. However, in order to obtain microscopic information, it is necessary to express $\delta_\alpha(a_H)$ as a function of the site-specific degrees of protonation, $\theta_i(a_H)$, $i = 1, \dots, N$. They are related to the macroscopic probabilities by

$$\theta_i(a_H) = \sum_{n=1,\dots,N} A_{in} P_n(a_H) \quad (9)$$

where the coefficients A_{in} are given by[8]

$$A_{in} = \sum_s s_i \pi_n(s) \delta_{n,\sum_{i=1,\dots,N} s_i} \quad (10)$$

Expressing the macroscopic probabilities in terms of $\theta_i(a_H)$ by inverting equation (9) and using the fact that $P_0(a_H) = 1 - \sum_{n=1,\dots,N} P_n(a_H)$, the chemical shift can be expressed in terms of the site-specific degrees of protonation as a lineal function

$$\delta_\alpha(a_H) = \delta_{\alpha 0} + \sum_{i=1,\dots,N} \delta_{\alpha i} \theta_i(a_H) \quad (11)$$

where $\delta_{\alpha 0} = \tilde{\delta}_{\alpha 0}$ and $\delta_{\alpha i} = \sum_{n=1,\dots,N} (\mathbf{A}^{-1})_{ni} (\tilde{\delta}_{\alpha n} - \tilde{\delta}_{\alpha 0})$ are the chemical shifts for each protonated state. An important advantage in using eqn. (11) instead of (8) is that the symmetry properties of the molecule can be incorporated

in the fitting process by assuming equal $\theta_i(a_{\text{H}})$ values for equivalent ionizable sites, as it is the case of the first and third carboxylic groups of citric acid.

In some molecules the chemical shift $\delta_{\alpha}(a_{\text{H}})$ only responds to the change in the closest ionizable site, say j , so that $\delta_{\alpha i} = \delta_{\alpha p} \delta_{ij}$, being δ_{ij} the Kronecker delta. Then, the expression for its specific site adopts the very simple form[16, 10, 15]

$$\theta_j(a_{\text{H}}) = \frac{\delta_{\alpha} - \delta_{\alpha 0}}{\delta_{\alpha p} - \delta_{\alpha 0}} \quad (12)$$

where $\delta_{\alpha 0}$ and $\delta_{\alpha p}$ are the chemical shifts of the fully deprotonated and fully protonated molecule, respectively, and can be obtained directly from the plateaus at high and low pH values of the curves of the chemical shift *versus* pH. However, in many cases, the influence of distant ionizable groups in the chemical shift cannot be neglected, and equation (12) is not accurate. The influence of distant groups can be due to direct influence *via* the electronic structure, conformational transitions, or even solvent effects.[8, 10] In the case of citric acid, the "cross terms" in (11) cannot be neglected and equation (12) can not be used. Actually, if equation (12) is applied to the two peaks of the two methylene hydrogens of citric acid, two inconsistent curves θ_j versus pH are obtained, which lead to contradictory values of the microscopic parameters. The inability of properly fitting experimental NMR data using equation (12) is most probably because changes in the charge states produced by pH variations are coupled with changes in the conformational properties of citric acid.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 *Ab initio* study

The citrate molecule has three carboxyl groups, one hydroxyl group and two methylene moieties. Two of the three carboxyl groups (terminal) are symmetrically equivalent. The third carboxyl (central) together with the hydroxyl group are attached to the central carbon atom. The "carbon backbone" of the molecule refers to the chain of five consecutive carbon atoms. The arrangement of this carbon backbone will be the main responsible to the different conformations.

To perform the conformational exploration of citric acid, different conformers are obtained by the variation of the dihedral ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 angles (Fig. 1). Notice that there are two possibilities for *gauche* conformation depending on the sign of rotation. Each of this dihedral angle could be in *trans* (*t*) or *gauche* (*g*) conformation. In the optimized geometries, the torsion angles deviate generally from the reference 180, 60 or -60 degree values because of steric and electrostatic interactions.

The conformational equilibrium of citric acid has been first studied by *ab initio* methods for the non ionized form. Then, the deprotonation of the non ionized form is used to generate the new structures for the mono-deprotonated form, di-deprotonated form and fully deprotonated. For each charge state, the

conformation	ΔG_{rel}	Φ_1	Φ_2	d(Ct ₁ -Cc ₂)	d(Cc ₂ -Ct ₃)	d(Ct ₁ -Ct ₃)	Proportion
<i>tt</i> 1 ₀	0.0	-176	174	3.0	2.9	5.0	88%
<i>tg</i> ⁺ 1 ₀	1.5	168	64	3.1	3.0	4.6	7.0%
<i>tg</i> ⁺ 2 ₀	1.8	-171	69	3.0	2.9	4.4	4.5%
<i>g</i> ⁻ <i>g</i> ⁻ 1 ₀	2.9	-59	-67	3.1	3.8	3.8	0.7%

Table 1: Relative Free energies in water (in kcal/mol) and dihedral angles (in degrees) of different conformations of charge state 0 of citric acid. Distances (in angstroms) among Ct₁, Cc₂ and Ct₃ carbon atoms of carboxylic groups. Labels of carbon atoms as indicated in Fig 1a. Conformational proportions calculated at 298K.

rotation of the hydroxyl, and carboxylic groups were sampled in order to establish all possible intramolecular hydrogen bonds.

By symmetry, one conformation with (ϕ_1, ϕ_2) pair of dihedral angles could be transformed in other with the (ϕ'_1, ϕ'_2) pair, where $\phi'_1 = -\phi_2$ and $\phi'_2 = -\phi_1$. In all the results, only one of these symmetric conformers is indicated. For conformations with *trans* and *gauche* angles, it is selected the conformer having the *trans* conformation for the ϕ_1 angle.

3.1.1 Fully protonated form of citric acid: Charge state 0

The conformational search of citric acid of the fully protonated molecule was carried out preparing initial structures with *gauche*⁺, *gauche*⁻ and *trans* conformations for ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 dihedral angles. In addition, different set of initial orientations of the hydroxyl and carboxylic groups were also sampled. Four different minima were found in solvent calculations. One for *tt*, two for *tg* and one for *gg* conformations (Fig. S1). Relative free energies in water and some geometrical properties of these minima are indicated in Table 1.

The *ab initio* MP2 optimizations in solvent gives that the *tt* conformation (*tt*1₀) is the most stable (88%) followed by the *tg* conformations (*tg*⁺1₀ and *tg*⁺2₀). The *tt*1₀ conformation is the most extended conformation although it is not completely symmetric ($\phi_1 \neq -\phi_2$). The hydroxyl is oriented through one of the terminal carboxylic groups, and both terminal carboxylic groups are oriented differently (Fig. 2a). For both *tg* conformations, similar free energies are obtained being the hydroxyl pointing towards the *gauche* or *trans* part of the molecule in *tg*⁺1₀ and *tg*⁺2₀, respectively (Fig. S1).

For each conformer, the distance between central (Cc₂) and terminal (Ct₁ and Ct₃) carboxylic groups is indicated in Table 1. With respect to the distance between terminal groups (d(Ct₁-Ct₃)), the tendency is as expected. *Trans-trans* conformation produce longer distances and *gauche-gauche* conformation makes more compact structures thus reducing the distance between terminal groups. Thus, terminal carboxyl groups are more separated in *tt* than in *gt* than in *gg*. However, the distance between consecutive carboxyl groups is not so straightforward. In *trans* conformation, the lateral carboxyl group has a similar

conformation		ΔG_{rel}	Proportion
$tt1_{-1}$	<u>H</u> Θ H	0	23%
$tt2_{-1}$	<u>H</u> Θ <u>H</u>	1.5	3.7%
$tt3_{-1}$	<u>H</u> Θ H	1.6	3.2%
$tt4_{-1}$	<u>H</u> Θ H	2.1	1.5%
$tt5_{-1}$	<u>H</u> Θ H	2.2	1.1%
$tt6_{-1}$	<u>Θ</u> HH	2.5	0.8%
$tt7_{-1}$	<u>Θ</u> HH	2.6	0.6%
$tt8_{-1}$	<u>Θ</u> HH	2.7	0.5%
tg^+1_{-1}	<u>H</u> Θ H	1.2	6.1%
tg^+2_{-1}	<u>Θ</u> HH	3.2	0.2%
tg^+3_{-1}	<u>Θ</u> HH	3.7	0.1%
tg^+4_{-1}	HH Θ	4.9	0.0%
tg^+5_{-1}	HH Θ	6.8	0.0%
tg^+6_{-1}	<u>Θ</u> HH	7.0	0.0%
$g^-g^-1_{-1}$	<u>H</u> Θ H	0.0	48%
$g^-g^-2_{-1}$	<u>Θ</u> HH	0.9	10%
$g^-g^-3_{-1}$	H Θ H	2.6	0.6%
$g^-g^-4_{-1}$	Θ HH	8.4	0.0%

Table 2: Relative Free energies (in kcal/mol) in water of different conformations for the mono-deprotonated form of citrate. Conformational proportions calculated at 298K.

distance to the central carboxyl group or to the hydroxyl group. The rotation of ϕ_2 angle makes the terminal carboxyl group Ct_3 to rotate towards the central carboxyl group side (g^+) or towards the hydroxyl side (g^-). In the first case, the $d(Cc_2-Ct_3)$ distance do not changes (as in tg^+1_0 and tg^+2_0) and in the second case this distance increases about one angstrom (as in $g^-g^-1_0$). Thus, the $g^-g^-1_0$ conformation has the closest distance between distance carboxylic groups, but it has the central carboxylic group more separated to one of the terminal carboxylic groups than in tg conformations.

3.1.2 Mono-deprotonated form of citrate: Charge state -1

In the $C_6H_7O_7^{-1}$ citrate anion, one of the three carboxylic groups is deprotonated. To indicate the protonation state of each individual protonated site, we have labelled each carboxylic group with “H” when it is protonated, or with “ Θ ” when it is deprotonated. Thus, there are three possibilities (HH Θ , H Θ H and Θ HH) to indicate the carboxylic group which is negatively charged. For tg conformers, the localization of the charge in one of the two terminal groups gives different conformers because the environment is different in each part of the molecule (one group is in the *trans* side and the other in the *gauche* side). In addition, the participation of a carboxylic group as an acceptor or donor of an intramolecular hydrogen bond is indicated by underlining the cor-

responding desprotonated (“ $\ominus$ ”) or protonated (“ H ”) site. Thus in $tt2_{-1}$ $\text{H}\ominus\text{H}$ all three carboxylic groups participates in hydrogen bonds (Fig. S2). The terminal carboxylic groups as donor and central carboxylic group as acceptor. Hydrogen bond is depicted if the geometrical criteria is simultaneously satisfied: distance between oxygen atoms less than 3 angstroms and angle O-H-O greater than 120 degrees.

In the Table 2 it can be seen that the most stables structure corresponds to $tt1_{-1}$ and $g^-g^-1_{-1}$ conformations with the same free energy. In both cases, the negative charge is situated in the central carboxylic group. In $g^-g^-1_{-1}$ conformation, an intramolecular hydrogen bond is established between the hydrogen of one lateral carboxylic group and one oxygen of the central charged carboxylic group (Fig. 2b).

The conformations with charge situated at the central carboxylate group has a global population of 88%, whereas those at the terminal carboxylate groups has a population of 12%.

Notice that $g^-g^-1_{-1}$ and $g^-g^-2_{-1}$ have practically the same coordinates of all atoms except one acid hydrogen. Only a shift in its position about 0.3 angstroms makes to protonate a lateral ($g^-g^-1_{-1}$) or central ($g^-g^-2_{-1}$) carboxylic group. *Calculations with intermediate positions of these hydrogen shows that this transition is produced without energetic barrier.*

3.1.3 Di-deprotonated form of citrate: Charge state -2

In the $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_7^{-2}$ citrate anion two of the three carboxylate groups are deprotonated. The most stable conformation is $g^-g^-1_{-2}$ (Fig. 2c) followed by $g^-g^-2_{-2}$ (0.3 kcal/mol), tg^+1_{-2} (0.8 kcal/mol) and $g^-g^-3_{-2}$ (0.9 kcal/mol) and $g^-g^-4_{-2}$ (1.0 kcal/mol). The gg conformers are the most populated (Table 3). The population of tt , gt and gg conformations are 0.2%, 19% and 81%, respectively.

The population of conformations with the symmetrical charged form ($\Theta\text{H}\Theta$) is 18%, where as the population with asymmetrical charged forms ($\text{H}\Theta\Theta$ and $\Theta\Theta\text{H}$) are 82%.

Great part of the population (61%) is distributed between of only two minima: the $g^-g^-1_{-2}$ and $g^-g^-2_{-2}$ asymmetrical charged conformers. The structure of these two conformers are very similar differing only in the position of the acid hydrogen. In these two conformers it is establish an intramolecular hydrogen bond between the hydrogen of the protonated carboxyl group of one end and the oxygen of the charged carboxylic group of the other end. Calculations fixing these acid hydrogen at intermediate positions indicates that this transition is performed without energetic barrier. For the monoprotonated forms of citric acid, there are three more pairs of conformers with similar structure: $g^-g^-3_{-2}$ vs $g^-g^-4_{-2}$, $g^-g^-7_{-2}$ vs $g^-g^-8_{-2}$ and tg^+1_{-2} vs tg^+2_{-2} . The conformers $g^-g^-4_{-2}$, $g^-g^-7_{-2}$, $g^-g^-8_{-2}$ and tg^+2_{-2} are asymmetrical charged whereas, $g^-g^-3_{-2}$ and tg^+1_{-2} are symmetrical charged. *POTSER això es pot relacionar amb que no hi ha formes carregades simetriques amb NMR, si el chemical shift és similar per les parelles en ràpid equilibri.*

conformation		ΔG_{rel}	Proportion
$tt1_{-2}$	$\underline{\underline{H\Theta\Theta}}$	3.4	0.1%
$tt2_{-2}$	$\underline{\Theta H\Theta}$	3.9	0.1%
$tt3_{-2}$	$\underline{\Theta H\Theta}$	4.8	0.0%
tg^+1_{-2}	$\underline{\Theta H\Theta}$	0.8	10%
tg^+2_{-2}	$\underline{\Theta\Theta H}$	1.2	5.3%
tg^+3_{-2}	$\underline{\Theta\Theta H}$	1.5	3.1%
tg^+4_{-2}	$\underline{\Theta\Theta H}$	3.5	0.1%
tg^+5_{-2}	$\underline{\underline{H\Theta\Theta}}$	5.0	0.0%
tg^+6_{-2}	$\underline{H\Theta\Theta}$	5.0	0.0%
tg^+7_{-2}	$\underline{H\Theta\Theta}$	5.1	0.0%
tg^+8_{-2}	$\underline{\Theta H\Theta}$	6.1	0.0%
$g^-g^-1_{-2}$	$\underline{\underline{H\Theta\Theta}}$	0.0	37%
$g^-g^-2_{-2}$	$\underline{\Theta\Theta H}$	0.3	24%
$g^-g^-3_{-2}$	$\underline{\Theta H\Theta}$	0.9	8.3%
$g^-g^-4_{-2}$	$\underline{\underline{H\Theta\Theta}}$	1.0	6.8%
$g^-g^-5_{-2}$	$\underline{\underline{H\Theta\Theta}}$	1.3	4.0%
$g^-g^-6_{-2}$	$\underline{\underline{H\Theta\Theta}}$	2.8	0.3%
$g^-g^-7_{-2}$	$\underline{\underline{H\Theta\Theta}}$	3.0	0.3%
$g^-g^-8_{-2}$	$\underline{\Theta\Theta H}$	3.3	0.1%
$g^-g^-9_{-2}$	$\underline{\Theta\Theta H}$	6.7	0.0%
$g^-g^-10_{-2}$	$\underline{H\Theta\Theta}$	7.6	0.0%
$g^-g^-11_{-2}$	$\underline{\Theta H\Theta}$	7.7	0.0%
$g^-g^-12_{-2}$	$\underline{\Theta H\Theta}$	11.1	0.0%

Table 3: Relative Free energies (in kcal/mol) in water of different conformations for the di-deprotonated form of citrate. Conformational proportions calculate at 298K.

Conformation	ΔG_{rel}	Proportion
$tt1_{-3}$	0.0	62
tg^+1_{-3}	0.4	3.9
tg^+2_{-3}	1.6	33
$g^-g^-1_{-3}$	2.6	0.8

Table 4: Relative Free energies (in kcal/mol) in water of different conformations for the fully deprotonated form of citrate. Conformational proportions calculate at 298K.

3.1.4 Fully deprotonated form of citrate: Charge state -3

For the fully deprotonated $C_6H_5O_7^{-3}$ citrate anion, we observe (Table 4) that the most stable conformation is $tt1_{-3}$ (Fig. 2d) followed by tg^+1_{-3} (0.4 kcal/mol). The gg conformation that was the most stable at charge state -2 is at charge state -3 less stable because of the impossibility of establishing an intramolecular hydrogen bond between terminal carboxylate groups.

3.2 MR spectrum of citric acid

Citric acid has two non-equivalent methylene protons ($\alpha = A, B$) corresponding to the two peaks of the NMR spectrum (Fig. 1). Both the separation of the peaks $\Delta(a_H) = \delta_A(a_H) - \delta_B(a_H)$ and the average position $\delta(a_H) = (\delta_A(a_H) + \delta_B(a_H))/2$ are pH dependent. Moreover, the two peaks are split due to spin-spin coupling, $J(a_H)$, between the two hydrogen atoms (Fig. 1b). The experimental dependence on pH of δ , Δ and J is shown in Figs. 4a, 4b and 4, respectively (from now, the explicit dependence on $\text{pH} = -\log(a_H)$ will be not put explicitly in the expressions). The NMR data points have been taken from Moore and Sillerud work [20]. The measurements were performed at 400 MHz and TMS was used as chemical shift reference. This data present very high resolution compared with previous NMR measurements of citric acid, which allows a detailed study of the microspeciation without need of auxiliary sources of information from related molecules, such as those obtained through methyl substitution of the carboxylic groups, which could perturb the binding and/or conformational structure of the reference citric acid molecule. For citric acid ($N = 3$), δ can be expressed in terms of Eq. (11) as

$$\delta = \delta_0 + \delta_{13}\theta_1(a_H) + \delta_2\theta_2(a_H) \quad (13)$$

where $\delta_n \equiv (\delta_{An} + \delta_{Bn})/2$, ($n = 0, 1, 2, 3$), and we have used the fact that $\theta_1(a_H) = \theta_3(a_H)$ in (11) since the terminal carboxylic groups are equivalent and $\delta_{13} = \delta_1 + \delta_3$, and accounts for the influence in the chemical shift due to both terminal carboxylic groups. δ_0 , the average chemical shift for the fully deprotonated molecule, does not need to be fitted, since it can be obtained from the plateau of the experimental δ versus pH data in the region of high pH values where the molecule is fully deprotonated (Fig. 4a). Moreover, δ_0 , δ_{13} and

δ_2 are not independent, since at low enough pH values, the molecule is fully protonated ($\theta_i(a_H \rightarrow \infty) = 1$) giving the relationship $\delta_0 + \delta_{13} + \delta_2 = \delta_P$, where δ_P is the average chemical shift for the fully protonated molecule. The value of δ_P is obtained from the plateau of the δ versus pH data at low pH values. Then δ (from Eq.13) is expressed as

$$\delta = \delta_0 + \delta_{13}\theta_1(a_H) + (\delta_P - \delta_0 - \delta_{13})\theta_2(a_H) \quad (14)$$

where δ_{13} is the only shift parameter to be fitted. In the same way Δ and J can be expressed as

$$\Delta = \Delta_0 + \Delta_{13}\theta_1(a_H) + (\Delta_P - \Delta_0 - \Delta_{13})\theta_2(a_H) \quad (15)$$

and

$$J = J_0 + J_{13}\theta_1(a_H) + (J_P - J_0 - J_{13})\theta_2(a_H) \quad (16)$$

respectively. δ_0 , Δ_0 and J_0 (*DONAR VALORS*) are obtained from the plateau of the Figs. 4a, 4b and 4c at high enough pH values, while δ_P , Δ_P and J_P (*DONAR VALORS*) are obtained from the plateau at low pH values. δ_{13} , Δ_{13} and J_{13} are adjustable parameters. On the other hand, using (9-10), θ_1 and θ_2 can be expressed in terms of the macroscopic probabilities as

$$\begin{cases} \theta_1(a_H) = \pi_1(3)P_1(a_H) + (\pi_2(5) + \pi_2(6))P_2(a_H) + P_3(a_H) \\ \theta_2(a_H) = \pi_1(2)P_1(a_H) + (\pi_2(6) + \pi_2(7))P_2(a_H) + P_3(a_H) \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

In order to simplify the notation, the microscopic probabilities have been numbered as indicated in Fig. 3. The conditional probabilities are not independent since they are constrained by symmetry: $\pi_1(4) = \pi_1(3)$, $\pi_2(7) = \pi_2(6)$. Using the normalization condition $\pi_1(2) + \pi_1(3) + \pi_1(4) = 1$, we obtain that $\pi_1(2) = 1 - 2\pi_1(3)$. In the same way, $\pi_2(5) + \pi_2(6) + \pi_2(7) = 1$ and thus $\pi_2(5) = 1 - 2\pi_2(6)$. Therefore, there are only 2 independent conditional probabilities, $\pi_1(3)$ and $\pi_1(6)$.

Since the experiment was performed at a citric acid concentration of 0.1 M, far from dilute and zero ionic strength conditions, we have preferred fitting the macroconstant values instead of using their thermodynamic values provided in [4]. The macroconstants can be related to the microscopic binding parameters, which are shown in Fig. 3: k_1 and k_2 are the microscopic dissociation constant of the terminal and central carboxylates, respectively; $-k_B T \ln v$ and $-k_B T \ln u$ correspond to the repulsive interactions of two terminal and central/terminal carboxylates; finally, $-k_B T \ln w$ represents the triplet interaction between three deprotonated carboxylic groups. Some basic calculations lead to

$$\begin{cases} K_1 = k_1(2 + p) \\ K_2 = k_1 u \left(\frac{1+2pq}{q(2+p)} \right) \\ K_3 = k_1 u \frac{pqr}{1+2pq} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where $p = k_2/k_1$, $q = u/v$ and $r = vw$.

The microstate probabilities, are given by:

$$\pi_1(3) = \frac{pq}{1 + 2pq} ; \pi_2(6) = \frac{1}{2 + p} \quad (19)$$

On the other hand, the other microscopic dissociation constants, related to subsequent deprotonation steps, can be easily related to the first two microscopic dissociation constants, k_1 and k_2 , and the microscopic interaction energy parameters, u , v and w

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} k_{12} = k_{32} = k_2u \\ k_{21} = k_{23} = k_1u \\ k_{13} = k_{31} = k_1v \\ k_{123} = k_{321} = k_{123} = k_{321} = k_1ur \\ k_{132} = k_{312} = k_2u^2w \end{array} \right. \quad (20)$$

which can be related to the macroscopic dissociation constants with the usual relationship between micro and macro dissociation constant [13].

In summary, equations (14-17) contain eight parameters to be fitted simultaneously to the experimental data in Figs. 4a-4c: three chemical shift parameters (δ_{13} , Δ_{13} and J_{13}), two microscopic dissociation constants (k_1 and k_2) and three microscopic interaction energy parameters (u , v and w). The fitting procedure has been performed using standard nonlinear regression routines in MatLab(**Register**)-(ref) and the robustness of the fitting has been performed using a Monte Carlo procedure in order to obtain accurate estimates of confidence intervals [34]. We apply this method to perform thousands of fittings with data values with added random errors up to 2σ and 3σ to obtain confidence intervals of 95% and 99% for all the parameters (**REPASSAR-HO**).

Table 5 shows the fitted values of δ_{13} , Δ_{13} and J_{13} with a 95% confidence interval. In Table S1 and S2, it is shown values of previous parameters from fitting procedures using 3σ added errors and with 99% confidence interval that indicates the robustness of the fitting procedure. In addition, if the fitting is performed to Fig. 4a and 4b data, without using the spin-spin coupling data, the results do not change significantly. The sequence $\delta_0 - \delta_{13} - \delta_2$, the average of the two peaks ?????, which increases monotonically ???with increasing pH???, indicates that the influence of the terminal carboxylate on the chemical shift is larger than that of the central carboxylic group. However, the behaviour of Δ is more complicated. While Δ_0 and Δ_2 are positive, Δ_{13} is negative, which would suggest conformational changes in the pass from the fully deprotonated to the mono-protonated molecule, in agreement with the *ab initio* calculations.

Moreover, the microscopic dissociation parameters are also obtained (Table 5) with very accurate values, giving an average value of $pk_1 = 3.65 \pm 0.03$ and $pk_2 = 3.17 \pm 0.03$. This means that the dissociation of the central carboxylic group is easier than that of the terminal group, in agreement with other experimental studies performed to obtain these parameters (Table 6). These values

δ_{13}	Δ_{13}	J_{13}	pk_1	pk_2
(0.259,0.292)	(-30.6,-32.9)	(0.014,0.122)	(3.618,3.686)	(3.146,3.198)

Table 5: Fitted values of NMR shift parameters and microscopic dissociation parameters for citric acid. The range of values corresponds to a 95% confidence interval calculated with a generation of errors of 2σ .

	pk_1	pk_2	pk_1-pk_2
from fitted NMR values, $I \geq 0.3$ M	3.65 ± 0.03	3.17 ± 0.03	~ 0.5
from Martin [13] $I \sim 0$ M	3.85 (exp)	3.35 (cal)	~ 0.5
from Pearce et al. [12] $I \sim 0$ M (exp)	4.10	3.23	~ 0.9
from Pearce et al. [12] $I = 0$ M (cal)	4.14	3.12	~ 1.0
from Pearce et al. [12] $I = 0.1$ M (exp)	3.79	3.02	~ 0.8

Table 6: Comparative of microscopic pk values for citric acid

were obtained measuring the microscopic constant of the central and terminal groups by blocking the ionization of the other carboxylic groups by methylation. The titration of the asymmetric dimethyl ester allows the direct determination of pk_1 . The other microscopic dissociation constant, pk_2 , are obtained from the relationships between micro and macroscopic dissociation constants [13], and from different pH titrations of selected methyl esters of citric acid [12]. The accuracy of these methods relies in the assumption that the presence of the methyl groups does not affect the binding properties of the central group. These values differ from those at infinite dilution [12, 13]. This is logical since the NMR experiments were done at a sodium citrate concentration 0.1M, and the minimum value of the ionic strength in the titration experiment was $I=0.3$ M. On the other hand, the values obtained from [12] at 0.1M of KCl solution are in good agreement with the obtained in this work.

Confidence intervals of the fitted interaction energy parameters (Table 7) shows that there are two parameters (v and w) which have high dispersion. Although the confidence intervals are high, the values clearly indicate that the repulsion between the two terminal deprotonated carboxylic groups is negligible ($v \rightarrow 0$) and the triplet interaction energy of fully deprotonated form is very large ($w \rightarrow \infty$). It is worth to note that the product of these two interactions is finite with a small confidence interval ($r = vw = 0.096 \pm 0.013$) (Table 7). On the other hand, the repulsion between two neighbour groups has a robust value of ($u = 0.28 \pm 0.05$). Finally, the relationship between microscopic dissociation constant introduced in Eq. 18 has a robust value ($u = 0.28 \pm 0.05$) but the relationship between repulsion energies of deprotonated carboxylic groups diverge ($q = (u/v) \rightarrow \infty$), due to the negligible value of the repulsion between the two terminal deprotonated carboxylic groups ($v \simeq 0$).

From the fitted parameters, it is straightforward to obtain the macroscopic dissociation constants (Table 8). These values differ from those at infinite

Parameters	Range	Mean
$\log(u)$	(-0.485,-0.638)	
u		0.28 ± 0.05
$\log(v)$	(-2.0,-10.7)	-6.4 ± 4.3
v		$v \rightarrow 0$
$\log(w)$	(1.0,9.7)	5.4 ± 4.4
w		$w \rightarrow \infty$
$\log(r) ; r = vw$	(-0.962,-1.081)	
$r = vw$		0.096 ± 0.013
$p = k_1/k_2$		3.02 ± 0.06
$\log(q) ; q = (u/v)$		5.8 ± 4.2
q		$q \rightarrow \infty$

Table 7: 95% confidence interval and mean values of fitted interaction energy parameters of citric acid calculated with a generation of errors of 2σ .

dilution[4]. This is logical since the NMR experiments were done at a sodium citrate concentration 0.1M, and the minimum value of the ionic strength in the titration experiment was $I=0.3$ M. There are several studies of dilute citric acid solutions at different ionic strengths [5, 7, 35]. Bénézech et al. [7] obtain a quasi linear decreasing dependence of pK s with ionic strength at different temperatures by fitting experimental values at different NaCl molalities taking into account an extended Debye-Huckel term and up to five adjustable parameters involving functions of temperature and ionic strength. The obtained trend is expected as the increase of the ionic strength diminishes the repulsions between deprotonated carboxylic groups, favouring the dissociation processes. The values reported for ionic strengths at 0.1m and 0.5m are in agreement with others experimental studies at 0.1M and 0.5M of KCl and NaCl solutions [5, 35]. The values obtained from fitted NMR values in the present work are in better accordance with the works performed with experimental conditions of high ionic strength (Table 8). In addition, good comparison is obtained with others experimental studies [6, 36, 37], and with those that improves the specific ion interactions taking into account the Pitzer theory [5, 35, 38]. **CHECK última frase???**

Finally, from Eqs. 19 and 20 it is possible to compute the probabilities of appearance of the different microstates and the other microscopic dissociation constants. From the values of interaction energy parameters (Table 7), the microscopic probability of the symmetric diprotonated species are calculated: 60% for $\pi_2(5)$ and 20% for $\pi_2(6)$ and $\pi_2(7)$. Thus, the symmetrical charged forms of the diprotonated species are more populated than the unsymmetrical charged forms. This is in agreement with the computations performed in this work, where the symmetric di-protonated conformers presents higher population (88%) than the unsymmetrical conformers. This is also in agreement with other experimental values which makes measurements directly from methyl-esters of

	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3
from fitted NMR values, $I \geq 0.3$ M	2.95 ± 0.03	4.13 ± 0.05	5.54 ± 0.05
from Bates et al. [4] $I \sim 0$ M	3.13 ± 0.02	4.76 ± 0.01	6.40 ± 0.01
from Pearce et al. [12] $I \sim 0$ M (cal) ^(a)	3.04	4.70	5.77
from Robertis et al. [35] $I=0.1$ M ^(b)	2.92	4.35	5.77-5.78
from Bénézeth et al.[7] $I=0.1$ m ^(c)	2.90 ± 0.01	4.34 ± 0.01	5.68 ± 0.02
from Robertis et al. [35] $I=0.5$ M ^(b)	2.82	4.13-4.15	5.41-5.44
from Crea et al. [5] $I=0.5$ M ^(d)	2.81-2.82	4.11-4.15	5.31-5.44
from Bénézeth et al.[7] $I=0.5$ m ^(c)	2.77 ± 0.01	4.12 ± 0.02	5.27 ± 0.04

- (a) calculated values from experimental determination of microscopic dissociation constants
(b) average values obtained from either KCl or NaCl solutions
(c) fitted values obtained from several NaCl molal solutions
(d) average values obtained from mixtures of NaCl and KCl solutions

Table 8: Comparison of macroscopic pK values of citric acid at 25°C

citric acid, as mentioned above [13, 12]. The prevalence of the symmetric species has been also observed by X ray diffraction experiments[39] (Table 9). Concerning the mono-protonated species, the prevalent species is the asymmetric one, with a microstate probability close to 100% ($\pi_1(3) = \pi_1(4) = 1/2$, which is the limiting value of $\pi_1(3)$ when $q \rightarrow \infty$ in Eq. 19), with a negligible appearance of symmetric mono-protonated species ($\pi_1(2) \rightarrow 0$). This is an intriguing fact since in citric acid, the ionization is produced in consecutive carboxylic groups, which nively would experience a higher electrostatic repulsion. However, the obtained result for $u = 0.28 \pm 0.05$, while we obtain $v \simeq 0$, indicating that the repulsion between neighbour groups is lower. This is in agreement with the computational results, where the same preference for the asymmetric form was observed (82%). The preference to ionize the neighbouring groups can only be explained if the conformational structure of the molecule is fully taken into account. The repulsive electrostatic interaction between terminal carboxylate groups in the symmetric form ($g^-g^-3_{-2}$) (Fig. S3) is transformed to an attractive interaction between terminal carboxylic and carboxylate groups because of an intramolecular hydrogen bond ($g^-g^-1_{-2}$ and $g^-g^-2_{-2}$). The role of the conformational structure can be also responsible of the particular form of the NMR Δ versus pH curve, as commented above. The prevalence of the asymmetric form is not in agreement with ref. [13], where the symmetric form is preferred (Table 9). According to this work, $u = 0.05$ and $v = 0.28$ (*repassar aquests valors*) in contradiction with our results. This discrepancy could be due to the fact that the methylation of one the carboxylates perturbs the conformational structure in the molecule, resulting in changes in the obtained microscopic constants. Moreover, results from ref. [12] are also in disagreement with the ones of ref. [13], which can be due to the different experimental procedure to make the titrations with the chosen methyl-esters of citric acid (*segur?*). Moreover, the

	π_2 (5)	π_2 (6) = π_2 (7)	π_1 (2)	π_1 (3) = π_1 (4)
	H Θ H	Θ HH or HH Θ	Θ H Θ	Θ Θ H or H Θ Θ
from fitted NMR values, $I \geq 0.3$ M	60%	20%	0%	50%
from <i>ab initio</i> calculations $I = 0$ M	88%	6%	18%	41%
from Martin [13] $I \sim 0$ M	61%	19.5%	44%	28%
from Pearce et al. [12] $I \sim 0$ M (exp)	79%	10.5%	11%	44.5%
from Pearce et al. [12] $I = 0.1$ M (exp)	75%	12.5%	14%	43%

Table 9: Comparative values of microstate probabilities of citric acid

other microscopic dissociation constants can be obtained from Eq. 20 (see Table 10), and they are related to the microscopic probabilities of mono-protonated species, Eq. 19, by

$$\pi_1(2) = \frac{k_{13}}{k_{13} + 2k_{12}} = \frac{k_{123}}{k_{123} + 2k_{132}} ; \pi_1(3) = \frac{k_{12}}{k_{13} + 2k_{12}} = \frac{k_{132}}{k_{123} + 2k_{132}} \quad (21)$$

For the fitted NMR values, $k_{13} = k_1 v \rightarrow 0$, because $v \rightarrow 0$, and $k_{132} = k_2 u^2 w \gg 1$, because $w \rightarrow \infty$. This values implies that the symmetric mono-protonated species are negligible and then, the steps of deprotonating one of the terminal carboxylic group, when other terminal carboxylic group is deprotonated is not probable. Moreover, the product of the two microscopic dissociation constants, $k_{13}k_{132} = k_1 k_2 u^2 r$, gives a value, $p(k_{13}k_{132}) = 8.97$, in agreement with the ones obtained experimentally [12] (Table 10). Moreover, the results obtained by Pearce et al. [12] give microscopic probabilities for mono-protonated species similar to the ones obtained form fitted NMR values and in disagreement with the ones obtained for Martin [13]. This discrepancy comes from the differences in pk_{12} and pk_{13} values. From Eq 21 we obtain $\pi_1(2) < \pi_1(3)$ for experiments made by Martin [13], and $\pi_1(2) > \pi_1(3)$ for experiments performed by Pearce et al. [12]. *One possible explanation of this different behaviour could be the different way used in each case in order to obtained k_{12} , one calculated from equilibrium ratios and the other from experimental procedure. (discutir millor)*

4 Conclusions

Conformational and ionization properties of citric acid have been studied by ab initio MP2 calculations using the SMD polarizable continuum model for solvent and statistical-mechanism treatment of accurate NMR titration data. Regarding the conformational details, it is obtained that the most extended conformation is the most stable at low and high pH corresponding to the no-ionized and fully ionized form, whereas at intermediate pH the molecule adopt also conformations that are more compact. The most stable conformers for $q=0$ and $q=-2$ charge states compare well with those obtained in the study of Khan et al.[21]. However, in their study, they found that *tg* conformers for $q=-1$ and $q=-3$ were most

	pk_{12}	pk_{21}	pk_{13}	pk_{123}	pk_{132}	$p(k_{13}k_{132})$
our results, $I \geq 0.3$ M	3.73	4.21	10.02	4.76	-1.06	8.97
from Martin [13] $I \sim 0$ M	4.60 (cal)	5.10 (cal)	4.40 (exp)	5.85 (cal)	6.05 (cal)	10.45
from Pearce et al. [12] $I \sim 0$ M (exp)	4.14	5.01	4.76	6.05	5.42	10.18
from Pearce et al. [12] $I = 0$ M (cal)	3.94	4.96	4.61	5.43	4.76	9.37
from Pearce et al. [12] $I = 0.1$ M (exp)	3.81	4.58	4.28	5.46	4.99	9.27

Table 10: Comparative values of other microscopic pk values of citric acid

stable in contrast with (tt and gg) for $q=-1$ and tt for $q=-3$ found in this study. Differences could be attributable to the *ab initio* method, basis set and calculation of solvent effect by single point calculations instead of optimizations in solvent medium. Wright et al.[22] performed classical molecular dynamic simulations of the fully deprotonated citrate anion in explicit water using their force-field parameters. They obtain that the extended backbone conformations of the anion in solution were the most probable. This is in accordance with the most stable conformers obtained in this study for the completely deprotonated form.

Moreover, the microscopic dissociation parameters are also obtained with very accurate values, giving an average value of $pk_1 = 3.65 \pm 0.03$ and $pk_2 = 3.17 \pm 0.03$. This means that the dissociation of the central carboxylic group is easier than that of the terminal group, in agreement with other experimental studies. With respect to microstate probabilities, it is found that analysis of accurate NMR titration data gives a population of the symmetric forms about 60% for diprotonated species, and 100% of asymmetric forms for monoprotated species.

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(a)

(b)

Figure 1: a) Extended representation of citric acid showing the two main dihedral angles responsible for the conformational variability. Carbon atoms in green, oxygen in red and hydrogen in white. The numbering of carboxylic group and the hydrogens resolved in NMR experiments are also indicated. b) Sketch of the NMR citric acid spectrum corresponding to the two sets of non-equivalent methylene hydrogen atoms, A and B. The two peaks show spin-spin AB coupling, characterized by a coupling constant J_{AB} . The average position of the two peaks ($\bar{\delta} = (\delta_A + \delta_B) / 2$), the separation between the two peaks ($D = \delta_A - \delta_B$), and the spin-spin coupling constant J_{AB} are pH dependent. More work would be needed to adscribe the hydrogen atoms A and B to the each peak of the spectrum, and there the adscription in the figure is only illustrative.

(a) $q=0$ $tt1_0$

(b) $q=-1$ $tt1_{-1}$ $H\Theta H$ and $g^{-}g^{-}1_{-1}$ $\underline{H}\Theta H$

(c) $q=-2$ $g^{-}g^{-}1_{-2}$ $\underline{H}\Theta\Theta$ and $g^{-}g^{-}2_{-2}$ $\underline{\Theta}\Theta H$

(d) $q=-3$ $tt1_{-3}$

Figure 2: Lowest energy conformers for citric acid (a), dihydrogen citrate (b), hydrogen citrate (c) and citrate (d).

Figure 3: Reaction scheme of citric acid, consisting of eight microspecies, numbered from one to eight. K_i are the macroscopic dissociation constants. k_1 and k_2 are the dissociation microscopic constants of the terminal and central carboxylic groups, respectively. u and v represent the interactions parameters between terminal-central and terminal-terminal dissociated carboxylic groups. Finally, w accounts for the triplet interaction between the three dissociated carboxylic groups. The fitted macroscopic dissociation pK values, microscopic probabilities and fitted microscopic parameters are also shown.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: Average chemical shift (δ), separation between the center of the peaks (Δ) and spin-spin coupling (J) as functions of pH. Symbols form ref. [20] and lines obtained from eqs. 14, 15 and 16.